

Zero-phase-delay synchrony between interacting neural populations: implications for functional connectivity-derived biomarkers

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ABSTRACT

Neural populations synchronise their activity with either zero-phase delay (activity in interacting regions occurs simultaneously) or a phase delay (activity in one region follows the other). In electroencephalography and magnetoencephalography functional connectivity analyses, artefactual connectivity can also occur with zero-phase delay. To minimise artefact, contemporary analyses typically exclude all zero-phase-delay interactions. However, the extent to which “true” interactions are resultingly lost—and the impact this has on the performance of functional connectivity metrics as biomarkers—remains unknown. Here, we show that most cortico-cortical functional connectivity occurs with zero- or near-zero phase delay, even where such connectivity is unlikely to be artefactual. Including, rather than excluding, zero-phase-delay connectivity increases the reliability, convergence with neurobiology (structure–function concordance, homotopic interhemispheric connectivity, and age-related connectivity changes), and prognostic ability of functional connectivity metrics. We find that excluding zero-phase-delay connections penalises functional connectivity strength between the strongest structurally connected regions: stronger structural connections lead to functional connections with phase delays closer to zero, mediated by a shorter signal propagation time. Our findings challenge generally accepted assumptions that zero-phase-exclusive methods are superior to zero-phase-inclusive methods.

Keywords: functional connectivity, biomarker, electroencephalography, zero-phase delay, zero-phase lag, signal leakage

Received: 7 February 2025 Revision: 5 August 2025 Accepted: 14 October 2025 Available Online: 17 October 2025

1. INTRODUCTION

Populations of neurons produce oscillatory electromagnetic activity (Bishop, 1932; Buzsáki, 2002). Through the precise synchronisation and integration of these oscillations, the brain produces cognitive function, sensory experience, and behaviour (Buzsáki, 2006; Lopes da Silva, 2013; Rodriguez et al., 1999; Singer, 1999; Uhlhaas et al., 2009; Varela et al., 2001; Womelsdorf & Fries, 2007). Studying these interactions, or functional connectivity, has provided insight into several cognitive processes (Dai et al., 2017; Hampson et al., 2006; Kang et al., 2011) and neuropsychiatric disorders (Du et al., 2018). Indeed, metrics derived from functional connectivity analyses have been proposed as candidate diagnostic or prognostic biomarkers for brain-based conditions (Du et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2020; Gholipour et al., 2022; Gil Ávila et al., 2023; Hong et al., 2020; Plitta et al., 2015).

The averaged oscillatory electromagnetic activity of neural populations can be non-invasively measured by electroencephalography (EEG) and/or magnetoencephalography (MEG; Singer, 1999). Brain regions are assumed to be functionally connected if the phase and/or amplitude (Engel et al., 2013; Varela et al., 2001) of their oscillations are statistically interdependent (Friston, 2011). Functionally connected brain regions can have perfectly synchronous activity (with zero-phase delay), or activity in one region may follow the other (producing a phase delay). However, the extent to which measured zero-phase-delay connectivity reflects “true” versus artefactual connectivity in empirical signals remains unknown.

There is robust evidence demonstrating the presence of “true” zero-phase-delay functional connectivity, replicated across species (Engel et al., 1991; O’Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021; Vicente et al., 2008; Witham et al., 2007). Spike-train recordings (Engel et al., 1991) have demonstrated that most functional connections between homotopic interhemispheric regions occur with zero-phase delay. Computational models suggest that “resonance-induced synchrony” (Gollo et al., 2014) facilitates zero-phase-delay connectivity: bidirectional information transfer between regions acts to mutually alter their dynamics into a stable zero-phase-delay pattern. Functions dependent on zero-phase-delay connectivity include maximising the reliability of information transmission and facilitating spike-time-dependent plasticity (Gollo et al., 2014), coding and binding features of sensory objects (Gray et al., 1989; Rodriguez et al., 1999; Singer, 1999), and others (Roelfsema et al., 1997; Steinmetz et al., 2000). Evidence from invasive recordings also shows near-zero-phase-delay connectivity (Uhlhaas et al., 2009), describing phase delays that are much smaller than those arising from axonal conduction

delays. An exemplar function of near-zero-phase-delay connectivity is neural encoding by hippocampal place cells (O’Keefe & Recce, 1993).

Artefactual functional connectivity due to signal leakage and volume conduction also occurs with zero-phase delay (Brunner et al., 2016; Hipp et al., 2012; Nolte et al., 2004; Srinivasan et al., 2007), as spatial blurring in signal leakage (Anzolin et al., 2019; Colclough et al., 2015; Hipp et al., 2012; Srinivasan et al., 2007) and field spread in volume conduction (Anzolin et al., 2019; Bastos & Schoffelen, 2016; Nolte et al., 2004) occur with zero- or almost-zero-time delay. This artefactual connectivity is unavoidable in EEG and MEG data. It mimics “true” connectivity (Anzolin et al., 2019) and may dominate the pattern of connectivity measurements (Hipp et al., 2012; Srinivasan et al., 2007).

Therefore, contemporary functional connectivity analyses typically exclude zero-phase-delay connections, prioritising the goal of limiting artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage and volume conduction (Colclough et al., 2016; Miljevic et al., 2022). However, the extent to which biologically relevant “true” connectivity is also lost when excluding zero-phase-delay connectivity is unknown. Including versus excluding zero-phase-delay connectivity may substantially alter the conclusions drawn from otherwise identical signals (Cociu et al., 2018), hindering progress in biomarker discovery (e.g., O’Reilly et al., 2017). No study, to our knowledge, has systematically assessed the effect of including versus excluding zero-phase-delay connections on the performance of functional connectivity metrics as candidate biomarkers.

Here, using empirical EEG data, we used a novel approach to quantify the proportion of zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity when signal leakage artefact was likely negligible. Then, we compared the effects of including versus excluding zero-phase-delay functional connectivity on properties desired in biomarkers: high test–retest reliability (Davis et al., 2020) and convergence with underlying biology (FDA-NIH Biomarker Working Group, 2016). Finally, we compared the performance of functional connectivity metrics derived from zero-phase inclusive versus exclusive methods as prognostic biomarkers for longitudinal changes in cognitive abilities. Thus, our analyses leveraged multiple performance criteria not trivially correlated with each other.

2. METHODS

2.1. Participants

We included participants from the AIMS-2-TRIALS Longitudinal European Autism Project, described here

(Charman et al., 2017; Loth et al., 2017). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants for being included in the study. In this analysis, we included 153 neurotypical participants (33% female), aged 6–31 years, from 5 study sites. For the analyses predicting longitudinal changes in spatial working memory, participants were split into children (6–12 years, $n = 41$), adolescents (13–17 years, $n = 50$), and adults (18–31 years, $n = 62$), [Table 1](#). Included participants needed at least 20 seconds of usable eyes-closed resting-state EEG data, a good quality (defined below) T1-weighted (T1w) magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRI) scan image, and a full-scale intelligence quotient ≥ 75 . We excluded participants with diagnosed neurodevelopmental conditions, intellectual disability, neurological conditions, mental health conditions (e.g., schizophrenia, bipolar affective disorder), and significant systemic disease (e.g., auto-immune conditions). Intelligence quotient was measured by the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence, Second Edition (Wechsler, 2011).

2.2. Electroencephalography methods

EEG artefact cleaning and source localisation were performed as per our group's previous work (Garcés et al., 2022).

2.2.1. EEG data acquisition

Four segments of 30-second, eyes-closed EEG recordings were captured. These short epochs were used to maximise comfort for young participants. Data were acquired at five sites: Central Institute of Mental Health (CIMH, Mannheim, Germany), King's College London

(KCL, United Kingdom), University Nijmegen Medical Centre (RUNMC, Netherlands), University Campus Bio-Medico (UCBM, Rome, Italy), and University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU, Netherlands). The following EEG systems were employed: Brainvision (CIMH, KCL, RUNMC), Biosemi (UMCU), and Micromed (UCBM), with sampling frequencies of 5000 Hz (KCL, RUNMC), 2048 Hz (UMCU), 2000 Hz (CIMH), and 256–1000 Hz (UCBM). All sites used 10–20 layout caps, with 60–70 electrodes.

Prior to source localisation, initial downsampling and bandpass filtering were performed, as per Hyvärinen (1999). Except for signals from UCBM (which were recorded at 256 Hz and not initially downsampled), EEG signals were downsampled to 1000 Hz, with an antialiasing filter (low-pass finite impulse response filter, Kaiser window, cutoff of 300 Hz, transition band width 100 Hz), using EEGLab (Delorme & Makeig, 2004). Then, the entire EEG resting-state recording (all four 30-second epochs and the segments in between them), with 10 seconds of data padding, was bandpass filtered between 1 and 32 Hz with a finite impulse response filter of order 2000, using a Hamming window, in both forward and backward directions, with detrending, using FieldTrip (Oostenveld et al., 2011).

2.2.2. EEG artefact cleaning

Only data from the 61 electrodes commonly used across all sites were retained. The following steps were performed: (1) electrode channels with poor data quality were removed, (2) temporal segments with large transient artefacts such as muscle bursts or movements were discarded, (3) independent component analyses were applied using fastICA for MATLAB, version 2.5 (Hyvärinen, 1999),

Table 1. Characteristics of included participants.

	6–12 years ($n = 41$)	13–17 years ($n = 50$)	18–31 years ($n = 62$)	Total ($n = 153$)	p value
Age (years)					
Mean (SD)	10.2 (1.9)	15.9 (1.4)	23.4 (3.5)	17.4 (6.0)	-
Range	6 – 12	13 – 18	18 – 31	6 – 31	
Sex					
Female	15 (37%)	20 (40%)	16 (26%)	51 (33%)	.25
Full Scale IQ					
Mean (SD)	111 (12)	108 (12)	109 (12)	109 (12)	.41
Range	76 – 139	77 – 133	85 – 142	76 – 142	
Site					
London	12	7	24	43	<.001
Mannheim	7	18	3	28	
Nijmegen	13	17	8	38	
Rome	0	0	16	16	
Utrecht	9	8	11	28	

This study included 153 participants aged between 6 and 31 years. For the analyses predicting longitudinal changes in spatial working memory, participants were grouped by age: children (6–12 years), adolescents (13–17 years), and adults (18–31 years).

to distinguish signal from noise, (4) artefactual independent components were identified and eliminated, and (5) channels discarded in (1) were interpolated. The common average signal across all channels was used as the reference. If more than 10 channels were eliminated in step 1, the participant's EEG data were excluded in this analysis, as the channel elimination was applied across all EEG segments. Such participants were, therefore, not included in the final sample of 153.

2.2.3. Source reconstruction

Source reconstruction was performed using individual-participant T1-weighted MR images (acquisition parameters detailed below). T1-weighted MRIs were segmented with Statistical Parametric Mapping 12 (SPM12) software (Penny W et al., 2006) into grey matter, white matter, cerebrospinal fluid, bone, soft tissue, and air. These probabilistic images were then smoothed (5 mm full width half maximum), thresholded, and resliced to produce binary masks of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ mm resolution for three tissue types: brain (including grey matter, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid), skull, and scalp. These binary masks were transformed to hexahedral meshes with FieldTrip (Oostenveld et al., 2011). All three considered tissue types were assumed to have homogeneous and isotropic conductivity: 330 ms/m for the brain and scalp (Gabriel et al., 1996), and an age-dependent skull conductivity of $3.958 + 62.77 \times e^{-0.2404 \times \text{age in years}}$ ms/m, in line with the BESA (BESA® | Brain Electrical Source Analysis: Home, 1995) recommended conductivity ratios. Segmentations were visually inspected. The forward model was derived with FieldTrip and SimBio (Vorwerk et al., 2018). For the inverse model, 1200 source locations of interest were defined in grey matter in Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) space, following a 3D cubic diamond grid. Source positions were transformed from MNI space to each subject's individual space with a nonlinear transformation using SPM12. Electrode positions were determined by transforming standard MNI positions to subject space with the same transformation, then projecting to the scalp surface. Source time series were estimated with a linearly constrained minimum variance beamformer (Van Veen et al., 1997), coded in FieldTrip, using a regularisation of 5% of the average trace of the covariance matrix. The 1200 sources were parcelled into 68 cortical regions of interest, as per the Desikan–Killiany atlas (Desikan et al., 2006). Each region comprised between 1 and 67 sources (median = 13). When there was more than one source per region, the representative time series for a given region was defined as the first principal component of all the source time series in it.

2.2.4. Cropping, down-sampling, and filtering

We chose 20-second eyes-closed resting-state EEG epochs (from a maximum segment length of 30 seconds) to produce functional connectivity adjacency matrices. This epoch length was chosen as a compromise between maximising the number of included participants and maximising network stability (Fraschini et al., 2016; Pullon et al., 2020).

We then further down-sampled the signals to 250 Hz. Data quality checks were subsequently performed.

We treated the whole 20-second epoch as a single window. Producing multiple windows has the advantage of better capturing moment-to-moment connectivity. However, longer window length better captures the “ground truth” (Pullon et al., 2020). Additionally, longer windows are needed to capture weaker connections (Pullon et al., 2020) due to the noise inherent to EEG signals.

The signals were then filtered into the conventional frequency bands: delta (1–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–13 Hz), low-beta (13–20 Hz), and high-beta (20–32 Hz). High-pass followed by low-pass filters were used in sequence, using two-pass (using the MATLAB function `filtfilt`), finite impulse response filters, of order 250. To reduce signal distortion, data padding of 500 samples (2 seconds) was used during filtering and while performing Hilbert transformations.

2.3. Quantifying phase delays

To quantify the phase delay between two signals $x_i(t)$ and $x_j(t)$, $t=1, \dots, N$ where N is the number of points in an EEG epoch, we first applied the Hilbert transform to obtain the instantaneous phases $\theta_i(t), \theta_j(t)$ for the signals $x_i(t)$ and $x_j(t)$, respectively. Then, the phase-delay distribution $\Delta\theta(t) = \theta_i(t) - \theta_j(t)$ was projected into the unit circle. We calculated the mean phase delay for each 20-second epoch by averaging the instantaneous phase delays across all samples within that epoch:

$$\tau_{i,j} = \text{angle} \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N e^{j\Delta\theta(t)} \right).$$

Note that “true” $\pm\pi$ -phase-delay functional connectivity also occurs between region pairs where “true” zero-phase-delay connectivity is prevalent, and has important functions (Hilgetag et al., 2001; Ni et al., 2009; O'Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021; Palmer et al., 2012). As $\pm\pi$ -phase-delay functional connectivity is also excluded by zero-phase-exclusive functional connectivity methods, for brevity, zero-phase delay and π -phase delay are subsequently referred to together as “zero-phase delay.”

2.4. Investigating where the effects of signal leakage are likely negligible

We graphically examined the relationship between the proportion of zero and near-zero phase-delay functional connectivity and Euclidean distance between region pairs. Artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage occurs at zero-phase delay (Gohel et al., 2017; Hipp et al., 2012) and its influence is a function of Euclidean distance between sources (Bastos & Schoffelen, 2016; Gohel et al., 2017; He et al., 2019; Hipp et al., 2012). Therefore, we explored whether there were Euclidean distances between brain regions at which the proportion of zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity did not vary as a function of Euclidean distance. Such a phenomena would suggest that artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage is likely negligible at these Euclidean distances.

Euclidean distance between region pairs was measured from the centroids of the regions, obtained from the FreeSurfer surface parcellation, measured per participant using individual T1w MR images.

In the absence of an established definition of “near-zero-phase delays,” we defined them as phase delays $< |0.3|$ radians from 0 or $\pm\pi$ radians. These phase delays comprise 19.1% of possible phase delays in a unit circle. Such phase delays are smaller than those arising from axonal conduction delays. For example, the phase delay caused by signal transmission delays along a (white matter) streamline of length 128 mm (the median streamline length in our dataset), assuming a white matter transmission speed of 4.5 m/s (van Blooijis et al., 2023) and a synaptic transmission delay of 0.75 ms (Katz & Miledi, 1965), for oscillations at 10 Hz, is approximately 1.83 radians.

By design, zero-phase-exclusive methods modify the connectivity strength value based on the magnitude of phase delay, while zero-phase-inclusive methods do not. Connectivity strength values are only unaltered by zero-phase-exclusive methods at phase delays of $\pm\pi/2$ radians, and approach zero as phase delay approaches 0 or $\pm\pi$. At phase delays of 0.3 radians, the measured connectivity strength of “true” (and artefactual) functional connectivity is decreased by 70% using the wPLI and *Img* COH.

2.5. Functional connectivity methods

We limited our selection of methods for comparison with those that characterise functional connectivity based on phase relationships, amplitude relationships, or a combination thereof; do not make assumptions about directionality of connectivity based on the sign of phase

difference (Stam & van Straaten, 2012); are bivariate; and are commonly used. Thus, we selected phase locking value (PLV; Lachaux et al., 1999), amplitude envelope correlation (AEC; Bruns et al., 2000), and coherence (Adey et al., 1967) as zero-phase-delay inclusive methods. We selected their methodologically corresponding zero-phase-delay exclusive methods: weighted phase lag index (wPLI, Vinck et al., 2011), orthogonalised amplitude envelope correlation (Orth AEC; Hipp et al., 2012), and the imaginary part of coherency (*Img* COH; Nolte et al., 2004), respectively.

2.5.1. Coherence and imaginary part of coherency

Coherence measures the consistency of relative amplitude and phase between pairs of signals at a given frequency.

Coherence is the absolute value of coherency, $C_{ij}(f)$, between signals i and j , defined as

$$C_{ij}(f) \equiv \frac{S_{ij}(f)}{(S_{ii}(f)S_{jj}(f))^{\frac{1}{2}}},$$

where $S_{ij}(f)$ is the cross-spectral density of signals i and j , $S_{ii}(f)$ is the power spectral density of signal i , and $S_{jj}(f)$ is the power spectral density of signal j . We used the Welch method to calculate power spectral density, as it has the advantage of handling signal leakage effects well (Welch, 1967).

Therefore, coherence $\text{Coh}_{ij}(f)$, is

$$\text{Coh}_{ij}(f) \equiv \left| \frac{S_{ij}(f)}{(S_{ii}(f)S_{jj}(f))^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right|.$$

The imaginary part of coherency only considers the imaginary component of the complex-valued cross-spectral density:

$$\text{Img Coh}_{ij}(f) \equiv \left| \frac{\text{Img}(S_{ij}(f))}{(S_{ii}(f)S_{jj}(f))^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right|.$$

2.5.2. Phase locking value

Phase-based connectivity methods assume that two brain regions are connected if the rhythm of their oscillations are similar, largely independent of amplitude relationships.

The phase locking value between the signals $x_i(t)$ and $x_j(t)$, $t = 1, \dots, N$, where N is the number of points in an epoch is defined as

$$PLV_{ij} = \frac{1}{n} \left| \sum_{t=1}^N e^{j\Delta\theta(t)} \right|,$$

where $\Delta\theta(t)$ is the difference of the instantaneous phases $\theta_i(t), \theta_j(t)$ of the signals $x_i(t), x_j(t)$. Here, we did not perform the permutation testing that is typical for the PLV (Lachaux et al., 1999), to enable comparisons with the other structural and functional connectivity methods used in this analysis.

2.5.3. Weighted phase lag index

The weighted phase lag index is derived by multiplying the phase lag index value by a multiplier based on the amplitude of the phase difference.

The weighted phase lag index between two signals i and j is defined as

$$wPLI_{ij} = \frac{|E\{Im(S_{ij}(f))\}|}{E\{|Im(S_{ij}(f))|\}} = \frac{|E\{|Im(S_{ij}(f))| \operatorname{sgn}(Im(S_{ij}(f)))\}|}{E\{|Im(S_{ij}(f))|\}},$$

where S_{ij} is the cross-spectrum between the signals i and j .

2.5.4. Amplitude envelope correlation and orthogonalised amplitude envelope correlation

The amplitude envelope correlation (AEC) detects amplitude relationships between signals, independent of phase relationships. The AEC between region pairs i and j is the magnitude of the Pearson correlation coefficient between the absolute values of Hilbert transformed signal i and the absolute values of Hilbert transformed signal j .

In the orthogonalised AEC, pairs of signals are orthogonalised with respect to each other prior to carrying out the AEC calculation. Orthogonalisation was performed (on a per-sample basis) in two directions (i to j , j to i), producing $i_{\perp j}$ and $j_{\perp i}$ time series, as per Hipp et al. (2012). $i_{\perp j}$, for example, was derived by

$$i_{\perp j}(t, f) = i(t, f) - i_{\parallel j}(t, f),$$

when

$$i_{\parallel j}(t, f) = a_{i,j}(f, T)j(t, f),$$

where $a_{i,j}$ is the regression coefficient obtained by ordinary least squares describing the linear relationship between i and j throughout the epoch ($t = 20$). The orthogonalised time series were then squared and log transformed, to make the time series more normal, as per Hipp et al. (2012). Then, power envelope correlations were

computed between i and $j_{\perp i}$, and j and $i_{\perp j}$ —the mean of the two correlation values was taken to be the undirected orthogonalised connectivity value between i and j .

2.6. Test-retest reliability

We quantified the intrasession test-retest reliability between two epochs recorded between 1 and 3 minutes of each other ($n = 99$). Intrasession test-retest reliability was used to reduce the confounding effects of circadian rhythm (Fafrowicz et al., 2019) and caffeine (Haller et al., 2013) on functional connectivity. Two measures of test-retest reliability were used: absolute agreement and consistency. Edgewise absolute agreement was quantified using the interclass correlation coefficient (ICC (2,1)). ICC values were interpreted as per Koo and Li (2016): 0.9–1.0 indicate excellent reliability, 0.75–0.9 indicate good reliability, 0.5–0.75 indicate moderate reliability, and 0.0–0.5 indicate poor reliability. Negative values were given a value of 0. We quantified the consistency of the whole adjacency matrix using Spearman's correlation coefficient, as per van der Velde et al. (2019).

2.7. Structural connectivity

Structural connectivity between 68 grey matter regions, as parcellated by the Desikan–Killiany atlas (Desikan et al., 2006), was quantified by using spherical deconvolution diffusion-weighted imaging. Diffusion imaging data were available from 2 of 5 study sites (KCL and Mannheim), comprising 50 participants (Table 2a). Spherical deconvolution diffusion imaging was used to overcome the crossing fibres problem that is a key limitation of traditional diffusion tensor imaging (Dell'Acqua et al., 2013). Connectivity strength between two regions was based on the streamline count between them, normalised to the value of 1, as per Chu et al. (2015).

2.7.1. T1-weighted cortical reconstruction using FreeSurfer

Signals from diffusion imaging were projected on to the cortical surface derived from each participant's T1w MR image. As previously done by our group (Pretzsch et al., 2022), all T1 scans were manually inspected; those with visible anomalies or significant movement artefacts were excluded. For each T1w MRI, models of the cortical surface using FreeSurfer v6.0 (<https://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/>) were computed. A detailed description of these well-validated and automated procedures is provided by Fischl (2012). In brief, FreeSurfer performs intensity normalisation, skull stripping, and an image segmentation using a connected-components algorithm.

Next, it generates a filled white matter volume for each hemisphere and, by fitting a deformable template, a surface tessellation for each of these volumes. For each subject, this yields a mesh (of triangular elements) for the inner (white matter) and outer (pial) cortical surface consisting of ~150k vertices (points in each triangular element) per hemisphere. Each of these reconstructed surfaces was inspected visually for reconstruction errors by three independent and experienced researchers. Scans were either accepted or manually edited after automatic pre-processing. Manually edited images were iteratively re-pre-processed and visually re-assessed.

2.7.2. Diffusion MRI pre-processing

Diffusion MRI acquisition parameters are detailed in Table 2b. Tools from Connectome Workbench (<https://www.humanconnectome.org/software>) were used to re-tessellate the T1w surfaces of each participant to the common tessellation of the “32k_FS_LR” template. This was done to reduce the number of vertices in each surface to 32,492 points, reducing the computational burden of the cortical projection step.

The diffusion series of each participant was corrected for thermal noise (Veraart et al., 2016) and Gibbs ringing artefacts (Kellner et al., 2016). Due to the lack of reversed phase encoding images, the *SynB0* framework (Schilling et al., 2019) was used to generate undistorted $b = 0$ EPIs

and these were used to estimate the susceptibility distortion field using *topup* (Andersson et al., 2003). Next, *eddy* was used to correct the diffusion series for artefacts caused by frame-wise motion and eddy currents (Andersson & Sotiropoulos, 2016), intra-frame motion (Andersson et al., 2017), and signal dropout (Andersson et al., 2016), as well as susceptibility distortions using the field generated by *topup*. The anisotropic power map (Dell’Acqua et al., 2014) was generated from the corrected data and used to calculate a rigid-body registration of the diffusion data to the subject’s T1w structural image in FLIRT (Jenkinson et al., 2002), and this transformation was applied to the entire diffusion series with a spline interpolation to align it with the T1w image; the bvecs were rotated with the same affine matrix.

2.7.3. Tractography and structural connectivity

Diffusion modelling was performed using the damped Richardson–Lucy spherical deconvolution algorithm (Dell’Acqua et al., 2010) in *StarTrack* (<https://mr-startrack.com>), with the following parameters: fibre response $\alpha = 1.5$; number of iterations = 300; amplitude threshold $\eta = 0.0015$; geometric regularisation $\nu = 16$. Fibre tracking was performed with the Euler-type algorithm according to the following parameters: minimum HMOA threshold = 0.002; maximum angle threshold = 45°; step size = 1 mm; minimum fibre length = 20 mm; maximum fibre length = 300 mm.

Each participant’s resulting tractogram was then converted to a connectivity matrix, as previously done by our group (Beyh et al., 2022). In brief, each streamline was projected to its nearest neighbouring vertex along the grey–white matter boundary surface (obtained from *FreeSurfer*) with a maximum distance of 3 mm. This resulted in a vertex-wise matrix, which was collapsed into a smaller matrix based on the Desikan–Killiany cortical parcellation, comprising 68 cortical regions of interest (Desikan et al., 2006). Several parcel-wise connectivity matrices were produced with the following edge weights: streamline count; log-transformed streamline count; hindrance modulated orientational anisotropy (HMOA; Dell’Acqua et al., 2013), a tract-specific measure of white matter microstructure; and median fibre length.

2.7.4. Structure–function concordance

Structure–function concordance was calculated on a per-participant basis ($n = 50$), using the Spearman correlation coefficient. For each participant, the adjacency matrix from each functional connectivity method was correlated with the adjacency matrix for the log-transformed streamline count, obtained from diffusion imaging.

Table 2a. Demographics of participants who had both EEG and diffusion-weighted imaging data.

Participants	KCL n = 28	Mannheim n = 22
Mean Age (SD)	23 (4.7)	15 (2.9)
Age Range	15 – 31	8 – 19
Mean FSIQ (SD)	109 (13.3)	110 (13.3)
FSIQ Range	85 – 142	77 – 133

FSIQ: full scale intellectual quotient.

Table 2b. Diffusion MRI acquisition parameters.

	KCL	Mannheim
Scanner	GE MR750	Siemens TimTrio
Sequence	SE-EPI	SE-EPI
Field of view	256 × 256 mm ²	256 × 256 mm ²
Matrix size	128 × 128	128 × 128
Number of slices	72	72
Voxel size	2 × 2 × 2 mm ³	2 × 2 × 2 mm ³
Echo time	67 ms	102 ms
Repetition time	12 s	12 s
Flip angle	90	90
B-value	1500 s/mm ²	1500 s/mm ²
Diffusion directions	60	60
No. $b = 0$ images	6	6

2.8. Predicting age

We assessed the ability of mean strength derived from each functional connectivity method to predict current age over and above head circumference. First, we calculated the R^2 from 10-fold cross-validation using head circumference as the only predictor of current age (model 1). Then, we added mean strength to this model (model 2). We used the change in R^2 (model 2–model 1) as the quantity of interest. In total, 147 participants had head circumference data. We excluded two outlier values (90 cm from a 22-year old and 66 cm from a 13-year old) as these likely reflected measurement inaccuracies.

We assessed whether model 2–model 1 cross-validation R^2 between methodologically corresponding zero-phase inclusive and exclusive methods (e.g., PLV vs. wPLI) was significantly different using permutation testing. We created a null distribution by permuting age 1000 times for each method pair in each frequency band.

2.9. Prognostic ability for longitudinal changes in spatial working memory

Spatial working memory was measured using the “Find the Phone” Task (Owen et al., 1990; Sjöwall et al., 2013). In this task, multiple telephones were shown on a computer screen and “rang” one at a time. Through trial and error, participants had to guess which phone was ringing. Participants were instructed that each phone would only ring once within a trial. The task was to remember which telephone(s) had already rung to avoid re-selecting that phone. Instances where a participant selected a phone that had already rung, or had previously been incorrectly selected, were counted as errors. The metric of interest was “total participant errors.”

For each functional connectivity method, we used the weighted, normalised pathlength in the theta band as the candidate prognostic biomarker. The theta band has been robustly associated with working memory (Bauer et al., 2021; Dai et al., 2017; Fell & Axmacher, 2011; Hyman et al., 2010; Jones & Wilson, 2005; Siapas et al., 2005). We only looked at connectivity between region pairs with a strong evidence base of being implicated in spatial working memory, including regions in the prefrontal cortex (MacKey & Curtis, 2017; Siapas et al., 2005; Wager & Smith, 2003; Wirt & Hyman, 2017), the posterior parietal cortex (Almeida et al., 2015; MacKey & Curtis, 2017), the anterior cingulate cortex (Wirt & Hyman, 2017), and the entorhinal cortex (Almeida et al., 2015; Salimi et al., 2021), as defined by the Desikan–Killiany atlas (Desikan et al., 2006). In total, there were 14 regions of interest in each hemisphere. Shorter weighted, normalised pathlengths reflect higher network efficiency.

Global network efficiency and pathlength have been associated with working memory performance (Langer et al., 2013; Stanley et al., 2015).

To calculate weighted, normalised pathlength, we first created weighted, undirected functional connectivity adjacency matrices (networks) with 28 nodes. One matrix was created per functional connectivity method. Each node corresponded to a cortical region of the Desikan–Killiany atlas implicated in spatial working memory, while the weighted edges were the functional connectivity strengths between pairs of nodes. Next, using the MATLAB brain connectivity toolbox (Rubinov et al., 2009), we inverted network edges to lengths (edges with larger weights produce shorter lengths). Then, we computed the *shortest possible* distance between all pairs of nodes. Finally, we calculated the average shortest distance between all pair of nodes to produce the weighted normalised pathlength. Formally, the shortest weighted path length $d_{i,j}^w$ between any two nodes, for example, i and j is defined as

$$d_{i,j}^w = \sum_{w_{ij} \in gi \leftrightarrow j} w_{ij},$$

where $gi \leftrightarrow j$ is the shortest weighted path between nodes i and j .

The weighted, average shortest pathlength (L) between node i and all other nodes of the network is defined as

$$L_i = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} d_{i,j}^w}{(N-1)},$$

where N is the number of nodes (28 in this analysis) and $d_{i,j}$ is the shortest path length between nodes i and j , when j is any node that is not i .

To calculate the normalised weighted pathlength, we used a normalisation process by creating 500 random networks by randomising the empirical network, while preserving the degree and strength distributions: each edge was rewired 5 times, with edge weights randomised every 5th step. The weighted pathlength of each random network was calculated, and then averaged across each of the 500 random networks to produce L_{rand} . The normalised average shortest pathlength of node i was calculated as

$$L'_i = \frac{L_i}{L_{rand}},$$

L'_i at each node was averaged across 28 nodes to produce the mean normalised, weighted pathlength (referred to as normalised, weighted pathlength).

Using general linear models, we compared the ability of normalised, weighted pathlength produced from each functional connectivity method to predict changes in

total participant errors between the time the EEG was recorded and a time 12–30 months in the future (mean = 19 months, SD = 3.5 months).

2.10. Penalisation scale

We created a penalisation scale to quantify how connectivity values would be altered by zero-phase-exclusive methods. The scale was between 0 and 1, where the most penalisable phase differences (0 and $\pm\pi$) were given a value of 1 and least penalisable phase differences ($\pm\pi/2$) were given a value of 0. Penalisation scale values were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Penalisation value} = \frac{|| \text{average phase delay} | - \frac{\pi}{2} |}{\frac{\pi}{2}},$$

where the average absolute phase delay was limited between 0 and $+\pi$. To examine whether stronger structural connections were more likely to be associated with more penalizable phase-delays, we calculated the Spearman correlation between the penalisation values and the structural connectivity matrix on a per-participant basis. This was only done for region pairs between which there were one or more streamlines.

2.11. Proxy of signal transmission time

We used a proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts. We divided the median length (distance) of white matter tracts between region pairs by a proxy of transmission speed. The median hindrance-modulated orientational anisotropy (HMOA) was used as a proxy of transmission speed, as white matter microstructural integrity can reflect myelination (Dell'Acqua et al., 2013) and correlates with nerve conduction velocity (Heckel et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2022). Additionally, the transmission latencies of evoked potentials (an established method of approximating transmission speed; van Blooijis et al., 2023) negatively correlate with white matter microstructure across studies (Evstigneev et al., 2013; Whitford et al., 2011).

2.11.1. Bootstrapping for mediation effects

We performed a mediation analysis to investigate whether the association between structural connectivity strength and the penalisation of the phase difference of functional connectivity was mediated by a proxy for white matter signal transmission time. We tested the significance of the indirect effect using bootstrapping procedures. Unstandardised indirect effects were computed for each of 1000 bootstrapped samples, and the 95% confidence interval was computed by determining the indirect effects at the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Most functional connectivity occurs with zero- and near-zero phase delay, even when artefactual connectivity is likely negligible

We quantified the distribution of the average phase delay of functional connectivity between brain region pairs (Fig. 1b). Between all region pairs across all participants, most measured functional connectivity occurred with mean phase delays of either zero-/near-zero or π -/near- π radians. Across frequency bands, alpha had the lowest proportion of zero- and near-zero phase delay connectivity (52% of all connections), while high-beta had the highest proportion (69% of all connections), Figure 1b–d.

In source reconstructed data, signal leakage (and not volume conduction) is thought to be the primary contributor of artefactual zero-phase-delay connectivity (He et al., 2019). To quantify the proportion of zero- and near-zero phase-delay functional connectivity when artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage was likely negligible, we used a novel approach. We leveraged the fact that artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage occurs at zero-phase delay (Gohel et al., 2017; Hipp et al., 2012) and decreases with increasing Euclidean distance between sources (Bastos & Schoffelen, 2016; Gohel et al., 2017; He et al., 2019; Hipp et al., 2012). Therefore, at sufficiently large distances where the percentage of zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity does not vary as a function of Euclidean distance, artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage is likely to be negligible. We examined this

Fig. 1. Quantifying zero- and near-zero phase-delay functional connectivity. (a) Where the percentage of zero- and near-zero phase delay connectivity does not vary as a function of Euclidean distance, artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage is likely to be negligible. This was found to be at Euclidean distances of ≥ 60 mm for all frequency bands. The number of pairs of regions per person at each minimum distance is listed above the graph. Histograms of the average phase delay of functional connectivity during an epoch concatenated across all participants: (b) between all region pairs, (c) region pairs > 80 mm Euclidean distance apart (where signal leakage is likely negligible), and (d) between homotopic interhemispheric region pairs. $n = 153$. The 8–13 and 20–32 Hz are the frequency bands with the lowest and highest near-zero phase-delay connectivity, respectively. *Italics*: the proportion of zero- (and $\pm\pi$) and near-zero (and near $\pm\pi$) connectivity. FC = functional connectivity.

Proportion of zero- & near-zero phase-delay synchrony is static beyond ≥ 60 mm Euclidean distance between region-pairs

Connectivity between:

c) Region-pairs >80mm apart
(signal leakage likely negligible)

d) Homotopic interhemispheric region-pairs
(median distance between regions = 57mm)

b) All region-pairs

relationship graphically (Fig. 1a), finding that the proportion of zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity did not vary as a function of Euclidean distance >60 mm. As expected (Srinivasan et al., 2007), this was true for all frequency bands. This finding is consistent with artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage being likely negligible beyond 60 mm, in keeping with previous estimates using simulated data (Anzolin et al., 2019; Gohel et al., 2017).

When limiting our analyses to region pairs 80 mm (where zero-/near-zero phase-delay connectivity was minimal) or more apart, we found that most functional connectivity still occurred with zero- and near-zero phase delay, in all frequency bands except alpha (where 47% of all functional connections occurred with zero- or near-zero phase delay; Fig. 1b).

Finally, we looked at homotopic interhemispheric functional connectivity as an example of connectivity known to robustly occur across species and measurement modalities (Cauda et al., 2021; Conturo et al., 1999; Engel et al., 1991; O'Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021). Remarkably, 83–89% of homotopic interhemispheric connectivity occurred with zero- or near-zero phase delays (Fig. 1b), despite a median Euclidean distance between them of 57 mm (IQR = 59 mm). This proportion was greater than that of 34 randomly selected pairs of heterotopic interhemispheric region pairs, in each frequency band (e.g., alpha: $\chi^2(1, n = 5,202) = 23.0$, $p < .001$; Supplementary Table S1).

In the Supplementary Results, we illustrate that the underlying neurobiology of interacting region pairs—as opposed to only any residual signal leakage and volume conduction artefact—contributes significantly to the phase-delay distributions seen in Figure 1c and d.

3.2. Comparing the performance of zero-phase inclusive versus exclusive functional connectivity metrics

3.2.1. Test–retest reliability is higher in zero-phase inclusive versus exclusive connectivity methods

In the alpha band, median edgewise ICC values were 0.20–0.71 across zero-phase-inclusive methods and 0.07–0.17 across zero-phase-exclusive methods ($n = 99$; Fig. 2; Supplementary Table S2). Absolute agreement was greatest in high-beta for all zero-phase-inclusive methods and lmg COH. It was highest in alpha for the wPLI and in low-beta for Orth AEC. The same patterns were also found for the consistency of each measure (Supplementary Table S3).

We found high absolute agreement for measured connectivity between region-pairs with a small Euclidean distance between them using zero-phase inclusive but not exclusive methods (Fig. 2; Supplementary Fig. S2). There are two plausible causes for this (1) neighbouring region

pairs reliably (structurally and functionally) connect to each other (Bullmore & Sporns, 2012; Conturo et al., 1999; Finger et al., 2016), and this functional connectivity occurs with zero- and near-zero phase delays and (2) artefactual connectivity (Hipp et al., 2012).

Absolute agreement at homotopic interhemispheric region pairs (Fig. 2) was high in all zero-phase inclusive methods, moderate with lmg COH, and low with the Orth AEC and wPLI. The relative test–retest reliability quantities across methods (Colclough et al., 2016; Fraschini et al., 2019) and frequency bands (van der Velde et al., 2019) are consistent with previous work, despite methodological differences.

3.2.2. Convergence with underlying neurobiology

We assessed the extent to which metrics derived from each functional connectivity method converged with underlying neurobiology by quantifying (1) structure–function concordance, as functional connectivity is influenced by monosynaptic structural cortico-cortical pathways (Baum et al., 2020; Chu et al., 2015; Finger et al., 2016; Fotiadis et al., 2024; Honey et al., 2009), (2) the ability of functional connectivity metrics to capture homotopic interhemispheric connectivity, and (3) their ability to predict participant age.

Concordance with structural connectivity is greater in zero-phase-inclusive methods

For all zero-phase-delay-inclusive methods, mean structure–function concordance was significantly greater than zero in every frequency band ($n = 50$, one-sample t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected), Figure 3. Concordance was not significantly different to zero for wPLI and orthogonalised AEC (one-sample t-test, $p > .05$). Surprisingly, concordance was significantly less than zero for lmg COH (one-sample t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected), Figure 3a and b. Concordance for each zero-phase-delay-inclusive method was significantly higher than that for its methodologically corresponding zero-phase-delay-exclusive method (paired-samples t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected; Fig. 3a, b). All findings were replicated when analysing each of the two sites separately, despite a difference in mean age between sites and large site effects in MRI analyses (Jovicich et al., 2006), Supplementary Table S4a and b.

Homotopic interhemispheric functional connectivity is robustly present with zero-phase-inclusive but not zero-phase-exclusive methods

Homotopic interhemispheric connectivity is robustly found across species and modalities (Engel et al., 1991;

Fig. 2. Edgewise absolute agreement across functional connectivity methods and frequency bands. Edgewise absolute agreement, quantified by intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC), for each functional connectivity method. In 8–13 Hz, for example, median ICC values were 0.20–0.71 across zero-phase-inclusive methods versus 0.07–0.17 across zero-phase-exclusive methods. High absolute agreement was seen between homotopic interhemispheric region pairs (off-diagonal edges in the adjacency matrix) in zero-phase-inclusive but not exclusive methods. High absolute agreement was seen between adjacent regions (main diagonal) in zero-phase-inclusive methods, but not in zero-phase-exclusive methods. Brain regions in the matrices were ordered by lobe and their proximity to each other (see Supplementary Fig. S2). The colour bar denotes the edgewise ICC value. Negative ICC values were limited at 0.

Mancuso et al., 2019; O'Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021; Schmahmann & Pandya, 2009; Vicente et al., 2008; Witham et al., 2007). We examined each functional and structural connectivity method's ability to capture this fundamental brain property. We calculated the edgewise mean functional ($n = 153$) and structural ($n = 50$) connectivity strength across all participants. On visual inspection, strong homotopic interhemispheric connectivity was found with all zero-phase-inclusive functional connectivity methods (Fig. 4a; Supplementary Fig. S2) and with structural connectivity (reflecting callosal connections; Fig. 4b). No zero-phase-exclusive methods showed prominent homotopic interhemispheric connectivity. Img COH showed significantly weaker connectivity between homotopic interhemispheric region pairs than between

non-homotopic region pairs (Fig 4a; Supplementary Table S5), which we explored in a *post hoc* analysis below. Of note, given the relatively large Euclidean distances between them (median 57 mm, IQR 59 mm), functional connectivity between homotopic region pairs would be minimally impacted by signal leakage.

The ability to predict current age is better in zero-phase-inclusive versus -exclusive methods

Given that brain functional connectivity matures with age (Collin & Van Den Heuvel, 2013; Edde et al., 2021; Fair et al., 2009), we quantified the extent to which age-related changes are captured by each functional connectivity method. We assessed the ability of mean strength derived from each method to predict current age over and above

b)	0-phase inclusive method			0-phase exclusive method			
	Mean SFC	SD	Freq (Hz)	Method	Freq (Hz)	Mean SFC	SD
Coherence	.098***	.043	1 - 4 ^w	Imaginary part of Coherency	1 - 4	-.038***	.039
	.108***	.040	4 - 8		4 - 8	-.061***	.048
	.105***	.039	8 - 13		8 - 13	-.048***	.049
	.106***	.045	13 - 20		13 - 20	-.055***	.051
	.113***	.047	20 - 32		20 - 32	-.072***	.048
PLV	.129***	.038	1 - 4 ^w	wPLI	1 - 4	-.001	.041
	.128***	.037	4 - 8		4 - 8	-.010	.040
	.119***	.033	8 - 13		8 - 13	-.010	.039
	.130***	.033	13 - 20		13 - 20	.002	.033
	.132***	.037	20 - 32		20 - 32	.001	.044
AEC	.123***	.042	1 - 4	Orthogonalized AEC	1 - 4	.006	.035
	.123***	.037	4 - 8		4 - 8	.010	.036
	.111***	.043	8 - 13 ^w		8 - 13	.006	.045
	.126***	.036	13 - 20		13 - 20	.008	.036
	.129***	.037	20 - 32		20 - 32	.005	.034

Fig. 3. Structure–function concordance is higher in zero-phase-inclusive versus -exclusive methods. (a) Structure–function concordance in the alpha band and (b) in all frequency bands (n = 50). In all frequency bands, concordance was significantly greater than zero with zero-phase-inclusive methods (one-sided t-test or Wilcoxon sum-ranked test, $\mu = 0, p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected). Concordance was not significantly different from zero for two zero-phase-exclusive methods (wPLI and orthogonalised AEC). Surprisingly, concordance was significantly less than zero for the imaginary part of coherency. Concordance for each zero-phase-inclusive method was significantly higher than that of its methodologically corresponding zero-phase-exclusive method in each frequency band (paired samples t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected). ***Concordance significantly different from zero, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected. ^w = data not normally distributed, therefore, one-sided Wilcoxon sign-rank test performed, otherwise one-sided t-tests performed. SFC = structure–function concordance.

Fig. 4. Edgewise structural and functional connectivity strengths. Mean edgewise (a) EEG functional connectivity matrices ($n = 153$) and (b) structural connectivity matrix ($n = 50$). Strong homotopic interhemispheric connectivity (seen at the off-diagonal edges in each adjacency matrix) was found with structural connectivity and with all zero-phase-inclusive functional connectivity methods. No zero-phase-exclusive methods showed prominent callosal connectivity. The imaginary part of coherency showed significantly weaker connectivity between homotopic interhemispheric region pairs than between other region pairs. Zero-phase-delay-exclusive methods did not show strong connectivity between neighbouring region pairs (main diagonal). Colour bars reflect connectivity strength, kept constant within each connectivity method; yellower colours denote higher connectivity strength. Brain regions in matrices are ordered by lobe and their proximity to each other (see Supplementary Fig. S2).

head circumference (which correlates with age). First, we calculated the R^2 from 10-fold cross-validation using head circumference as the only predictor of current age (model 1, cross-validation $R^2 = .27$). Then, we added mean strength to this model (model 2). The subsequent change in R^2 (model 2–model 1) is reported in Table 3a, $n = 145$. Across all frequency bands, model 2–model 1 R^2 was greater in a zero-phase-inclusive method than in its methodologically corresponding zero-phase-exclusive method; permutation analysis showed that this was statistically significant (false discovery rate corrected) in 10 of 15 comparisons.

3.2.3. Prognostic ability for longitudinal changes in spatial working memory is higher in zero-phase-inclusive versus -exclusive methods

We explored the ability of metrics derived from each functional connectivity method to act as prognostic biomarkers (Pletcher & Pignone, 2011) for longitudinal changes in spatial working memory ability, above and beyond current working memory abilities. We chose spatial working memory as an outcome measure because it has highly specific associations with functional connectivity (Dai et al., 2017; Fox et al., 2005; Hampson et al., 2006; Kang et al., 2011)

and altered working memory is implicated in several neuropsychiatric conditions (Alloway et al., 2009; Chai et al., 2018; Gathercole & Alloway, 2006).

We found significant pathlength \times age interactions in general linear models predicting changes in spatial working memory performance, when analysing all 6–31-year-old participants together (examples for coherence and *Img COH* provided in Supplementary Tables S6 and S7). Therefore, children (6–12 years, $n = 32$), adolescents (13–17 years, $n = 41$), and adults (18–31 years, $n = 36$) were analysed separately. Model covariates (selected using Akaike information criterion) were kept constant within each age group.

A main effect of network pathlength was only found for methods sensitive to zero-phase-delay connectivity: coherence in children ($\beta = 3.8$, $SE = 1.5$, $p = .014$; full model $F_{3/28} = 4.01$, $p = .017$) and PLV in adults ($\beta = -2.6$, $SE = 1.1$, $p = .027$; full model $F_{3/32} = 18.53$, $p = .003$), Supplementary Tables S8 and S9. For these statistically significant findings, we used leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) to quantify model performance (Table 3b). First, we calculated the LOOCV R^2 using covariates (model 1). Then, we added weighted, normalised pathlength to this model (model 2). Model 2–model 1 LOOCV R^2 increased by .101 for coherence in children and .074 for PLV in

Table 3a. Prediction of current age is greater in zero-phase-inclusive versus -exclusive methods.

Freq (Hz)	0-phase-inclusive method	Model 2 – 1 cross validation R^2	0-phase-exclusive method	Model 2 – 1 cross validation R^2	p_{FDR} permute
1 - 4	Coherence	.04	Imaginary part of Coherency	.02	.746
4 - 8		.09		.02	.041
8 - 13		.06		.05	.905
13 - 20		.07		-.02	.020
20 - 32		.01		-.01	.070
1 - 4	PLV	.05	wPLI	-.01	.010
4 - 8		.12		.02	.015
8 - 13		.16		.11	.101
13 - 20		.11		.01	.041
20 - 32		.10		.04	.015
1 - 4	AEC	.04	Orthogonalized AEC	.00	.285
4 - 8		.10		-.01	.041
8 - 13		.15		.02	.000
13 - 20		.14		.02	.041
20 - 32		.15		-.01	.000

Values show model 2–model 1 10-fold cross validation R^2 ($n = 145$) for each functional connectivity method and frequency band. Model 1: *current age ~ head circumference* (model 1 cross-validation $R^2 = .27$). Model 2: *current age ~ head circumference + mean strength*.

Table 3b. Prediction of longitudinal changes in spatial working memory performance is greater in zero-phase-inclusive versus -exclusive methods.

Age Group	Model 1 covariates	Model 1 R ²	Covariate added in model 2:	Model 2 R ²	Model 2–Model 1 R ²
6–12 years (n = 32)	Age + T1 SWM	.006	Coh PL*	.107	.101
			Img COH PL	.001	-.005
18–31 years (n = 36)	Age + T1 SWM + T2-T1 time interval	.489	PLV PL*	.563	.074
			wPLI PL	.453	-.036

In models predicting longitudinal changes in spatial working memory performance, a significant main effect of functional connectivity-derived pathlength was only found for coherence in the 6–12-year group and PLV in the 18–31-year group. For these models, and their corresponding zero-phase-exclusive methods, we report model 2–model 1 leave-one-out cross-validation R². Model 1: *longitudinal change in spatial working memory ~ covariates*. Model 2: *longitudinal change in spatial working memory ~ covariates + functional connectivity-derived pathlength*. *Significant main effect of covariate in general linear model ($p < .05$). SWM = spatial working memory, T1 = time point 1, T2 = time point 2, PL = pathlength.

adults. For comparison in their methodologically corresponding zero-phase-exclusive methods, model 2–model 1 LOOCV R² decreased by .005 for Img COH and .036 for wPLI.

3.3. Post hoc analyses

An unexpected finding from our analyses was negative structure–function concordance with Img COH. We theorised that this was because the strongest structural connections had the most “penalised” functional connections when using Img COH, based on the following logic: stronger structural connections result in quicker (decreased) signal transmission time between region pairs (Westerhausen et al., 2006; Whitford et al., 2011). Quicker transmission time means that oscillatory activity at each connected region pair occurs with smaller time delays, and therefore, smaller phase delays. Zero-phase-exclusive methods may penalise, rather than merely exclude, functional connectivity at near-zero-phase delays (a salient methodological detail is that zero-phase-exclusive methods modify the connectivity strength value based on the magnitude of phase delay, while zero-phase-inclusive methods do not). Hence, stronger structural connections may lead to weaker functional connections with some zero-phase-exclusive methods.

To test this, we hypothesised that (1) the connectivity strength values of zero- and near-zero phase-delay connections are penalised, and not merely excluded, if derived from zero-phase-exclusive methods. (2) Stronger structural connections lead to functional connections with more penalisable phase delays, mediated by quicker possible white matter transmission time. We expected a partial mediation, as strong structural connections such as the corpus callosum also produce zero-phase-delay functional connectivity through resonance-induced synchrony. (3) Structural connections that allow the quickest connectivity between region pairs result in the weakest functional connectivity if derived from Img COH.

3.3.1. Near-zero-phase-delay functional connectivity may be penalised and not merely excluded by zero-phase-delay-exclusive methods

We inspected the relationship between absolute phase delay and functional connectivity strength ($n = 153$), between region pairs where signal leakage is likely negligible (region pairs ≥ 80 mm apart), Figure 5. With zero-phase-inclusive methods, the median connectivity strength was significantly higher for near-zero/near- π phase-delay connectivity than connectivity at other phase delays, in all frequency bands (Fig. 5b). For Img COH and wPLI, the opposite was true: median connectivity strength was significantly lower for near-zero/near- π phase-delay connectivity than connectivity at other phase delays. For orthogonalised AEC, median connectivity strength was similar between near-zero phase delay and other phase-delay connectivity, in keeping with the milder form of orthogonalisation we used compared with others (Brookes et al., 2012; Hipp et al., 2012). Therefore, zero- and near-zero phase-delay functional connectivity may be penalised, and not merely excluded, by zero-phase-exclusive methods.

3.3.2. Stronger structural connectivity leads to functional connectivity with more penalisable phase delays, mediated by shorter white matter transmission times

We hypothesised that the stronger a structural connection, the more likely it was to produce functional connectivity with phase delays closer to zero, penalised by zero-phase-exclusive methods. The mean correlation between streamline count and penalisability of phase delays was significantly greater than 0 for all frequency bands ($n = 50$, one-sample t-test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected), Figure 6a. Hence, stronger structural connectivity led to functional connectivity with phase delays more penalisable by zero-phase-exclusive methods.

Fig. 5. When signal leakage is likely negligible, most functional connectivity occurs with near-zero phase delay, penalised by zero-phase-exclusive methods. (a) The relationship between absolute phase delay and functional connectivity strength (yellow colours denote higher density of scatter points) and (b) a comparison of edge strength when functional connectivity has zero/near-zero versus non-near-zero phase delays, for region pairs >80 mm Euclidean distance apart (where artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage is likely negligible). For zero-phase-inclusive methods, across all frequency bands, median strength was significantly higher for near-zero-phase-delay connections than connections with non-near-zero phase delays. For the imaginary part of coherency and wPPI, across all frequency bands, the median strength was significantly lower for near-zero phase-delay connections than for non-near-zero phase-delay connections. For orthogonalised AEC, median strength was similar between near-zero and non-near-zero phase-delay connections. Zero-phase-exclusive methods modify the connectivity strength value based on the magnitude of phase delay, while zero-phase-inclusive methods do not. Therefore, zero-phase-exclusive methods may penalise, rather than merely exclude, zero- and near-zero phase-delay connections. * $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected. FC = functional connectivity.

b) Comparison of the median strength of zero / near-zero versus non-near-zero phase-delay functional connectivity

0-phase-inclusive-method	Freq (Hz)	Median FC strength		0-phase-exclusive-method	Freq (Hz)	Median FC strength	
		Near-zero phase delay	Other phase delay			Near-zero phase delay	Other phase delay
Coherence	1 - 4*	.52	.39	Imaginary part of Coherency	1 - 4*	.11	.13
	4 - 8*	.52	.39		4 - 8*	.12	.15
	8 - 13*	.51	.40		8 - 13*	.14	.16
	13 - 20*	.48	.38		13 - 20*	.15	.17
	20 - 32*	.46	.37		20 - 32*	.17	.19
PLV	1 - 4*	.36	.17	WPLI	1 - 4*	.06	.16
	4 - 8*	.34	.15		4 - 8*	.06	.14
	8 - 13*	.32	.16		8 - 13*	.06	.16
	13 - 20*	.28	.11		13 - 20*	.04	.10
	20 - 32*	.26	.09		20 - 32*	.04	.08
AFC	1 - 4*	.21	.10	Orth AFC	1 - 4*	.09	.08
	4 - 8*	.22	.10		4 - 8	.08	.08
	8 - 13*	.20	.10		8 - 13	.08	.07
	13 - 20*	.17	.07		13 - 20*	.06	.06
	20 - 32*	.12	.05		20 - 32*	.04	.04

Fig. 5 (continued)

a) Correlation between structural connectivity strength and penalisation values

Freq (Hz)	Spearman's Correlation	SD
1 - 4	.092***	.039
4 - 8	.098***	.036
8 - 13	.096***	.036
13 - 20	.092***	.031
20 - 32	.095***	.042

b)

c) Mediation analysis statistics for the model in b), for each frequency band

Freq (Hz)	Total effect (x10 ⁻³)	Average direct effect (x10 ⁻³)	a	b (x10 ⁻⁶)	Average causal mediation effect (x10 ⁻³)	Proportion mediated [95% confidence interval]
1 - 4	2.97***	2.32***	-159***	-4.04***	0.64	.217 [.175 - .260]
4 - 8	2.61***	2.08***	-159***	-3.33***	0.53	.203 [.160 - 0.260]
8 - 13	3.86***	2.96***	-159***	-5.67***	0.90	.234 [.200 - .280]
13 - 20	2.64***	1.92***	-159***	-4.49***	0.71	.271 [.225 - .330]
20 - 32	2.17***	1.57***	-159***	-3.78***	0.60	.277 [.220 - .350]

Fig. 6. Stronger structural connectivity leads to functional connectivity with phase delays closer to 0 or $\pm\pi$, mediated by a proxy of shorter white matter transmission time. (a) We created a penalisation scale between 0 and 1, where phase delays most penalised by zero-phase-exclusive methods (0 and $\pm\pi$) have a value of 1 and phase delays least penalised ($\pm\pi/2$) have a value of 0. The mean correlation across participants between streamline count and penalisability of phase delays was significantly greater than 0 for all frequency bands, $n = 50$ ($***p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected, one-sample t-test, $\mu = 0$). (b) and (c) We created a proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts. The effect of structural connectivity strength on the penalisability of the phase delay of functional connectivity was partially mediated by the proxy of white matter transmission time, across all frequency bands. All effects were statistically significant ($*** = p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected). SD = standard deviation.

To test whether this relationship was mediated by quicker signal transmission time through white matter connections, we used a proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts. Across all frequency bands, we found that the effect of structural connectivity strength on the

penalisability of the phase delay of functional connectivity was significantly partially mediated by the proxy of white matter transmission time (e.g., proportion of the direct effect mediated by the proxy of signal transmission time was .234 [95% confidence intervals, calculated using 1000

b) Spearman's correlation between the proxy of white matter signal transmission time and functional connectivity strength

0-phase-inclusive-method	Freq (Hz)	Mean correlation	SD	0-phase-exclusive-method	Freq (Hz)	Mean correlation	SD
Coherence	1 - 4	-.132***	.060	Imaginary part of Coherency	1 - 4	.051***	.062
	4 - 8	-.120***	.058		4 - 8	.078***	.062
	8 - 13	-.170***	.063		8 - 13	.083***	.060
	13 - 20	-.147***	.072		13 - 20	.071***	.070
	20 - 32	-.148***	.052		20 - 32	.087***	.067
PLV	1 - 4	-.156***	.060	wPLI	1 - 4	-.007	.053
	4 - 8	-.160***	.060		4 - 8	.004	.060
	8 - 13	-.206***	.058		8 - 13	-.033*	.062
	13 - 20	-.180***	.064		13 - 20	.000	.054
	20 - 32	-.175***	.063		20 - 32	-.005	.071
AEC	1 - 4	-.155***	.056	Orthogonalized AEC	1 - 4	-.012	.056
	4 - 8	-.163***	.063		4 - 8	-.022	.063
	8 - 13	-.192***	.071		8 - 13	-.045**	.065
	13 - 20	-.173***	.067		13 - 20	-.015	.059
	20 - 32	-.172***	.067		20 - 32	-.007	.057

Fig. 7. Structural connections with shorter signal transmission time are associated with weaker functional connectivity with some zero-phase-exclusive methods. We created a proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts. The quicker (shorter) the proxy of signal transmission time through structural connections, the stronger the functional connectivity value for all zero-phase-inclusive methods (one-sample t test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected), (a) shown graphically for alpha and (b) tabulated for all frequency bands ($n = 50$). This was also the case for alpha (but not other frequency bands) in wPLI ($p < .05$, Bonferroni corrected) and orthogonalised AEC ($p < .001$, Bonferroni corrected). For the Img COH, the quicker the proxy of structural transmission time, the weaker the functional connectivity strength, in all frequency bands (one-sample t-test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected). Such a relationship is inconsistent with the literature. *** $p < .0001$, ** $p < .001$, * $p < .05$ (Bonferroni corrected).

bootstrapped samples = .197–.270] in alpha; Fig. 6b, c). The mediation was strongest in higher frequency bands, consistent with stronger structure–function concordance in higher frequency bands in zero-phase-inclusive methods (Fig. 3b).

3.3.3. Structural connections with shorter signal transmission time are associated with weaker functional connectivity with some zero-phase-exclusive methods

We found that the shorter the proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts, the stronger the functional connectivity value was for all zero-phase-inclusive methods (one-sample t-test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected), Figure 7. This is the expected biological relationship (Bassett & Bullmore, 2017; Bullmore & Sporns, 2012; Cabral et al., 2014). This was also the case for the alpha band in wPLI ($p < .05$, Bonferroni corrected) and orthogonalised AEC ($p < .001$, Bonferroni corrected), but no other frequency bands when using these methods. Note that alpha has the smallest proportion of near-zero-phase-delay connectivity (Fig. 1b). For Img COH, the shorter the proxy of signal transmission time through white matter tracts, the weaker the functional connectivity strength, in all frequency bands (one-sample t-test, $\mu = 0$, $p < .0001$, Bonferroni corrected). This is inconsistent with prior network literature (Bassett & Bullmore, 2017; Bullmore & Sporns, 2012; Cabral et al., 2014).

Thus, the structural connections that are prioritised in brain through quick structural pathways may be penalised by some zero-phase-delay-exclusive functional connectivity methods.

4. DISCUSSION

We demonstrated that most interactions between cortical region pairs occur with zero- and near-zero phase delay. We used a novel approach to show that this is also the case when artefactual connectivity due to signal leakage is likely negligible. Including zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity increased test–retest reliability, convergence with neurobiology (concordance with structural connectivity, ability to capture homotopic interhemispheric connectivity, and ability to predict chronological age) and prognostic ability for longitudinal changes in cognitive ability. Thereby, through converging lines of evidence, we show that functional connectivity metrics that include zero- and near-zero phase-delay connections have more properties desired in candidate biomarkers. We propose that the decreased structure–function concordance, ability to capture age, and ability to predict longitudinal changes in cognition associated with zero-

phase-exclusive methods are due to their penalisation of most “true” cortico-cortical functional connectivity.

We investigated homotopic interhemispheric connectivity as an example of structural and functional connectivity robustly found across species (Engel et al., 1991; Mancuso et al., 2019; O’Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021; Schmahmann & Pandya, 2009; Vicente et al., 2008; Witham et al., 2007). We captured conspicuous homotopic connections using structural connectivity and zero-phase-inclusive functional connectivity methods. We found that they were either inconspicuous or penalised when using zero-phase-exclusive methods. In contrast, a previous study (Hipp et al., 2012) captured connectivity between sensory homotopic region pairs using orthogonalised AEC. However, given our and others’ (Engel et al., 1991; O’Reilly & Elsabbagh, 2021) finding that homotopic region pairs predominantly interact with zero- and near-zero-phase delay, our findings are expected. We see the inability to capture this fundamental feature of brain connectivity as a key weakness of zero-phase-exclusive methods.

We found that structure–function concordance was significantly greater when using zero-phase-inclusive than when using zero-phase-exclusive methods. This is consistent with a previous small study of 17 participants (Finger et al., 2016). Additionally, we were surprised that with some zero-phase-exclusive methods, here Img COH, the strongest structural connections paradoxically had the weakest functional connections. We showed that this was because stronger structural connectivity led to functional connectivity with phase delays closer to zero, mediated by a proxy of shorter signal transmission times. Then, we showed that functional connectivity at near-zero-phase delays had penalised strength when derived from some zero-phase-exclusive methods. Hence, for Img COH, we found that region pairs connected by white matter tracts with the quickest possible signal transmission times had the weakest functional connections. This relationship is inconsistent with the network literature (Bassett & Bullmore, 2017; Bullmore & Sporns, 2012; Cabral et al., 2014).

Predictive validity for longitudinal changes in spatial working memory performance, as well as the ability to predict current age, was substantially greater when zero- and near-zero phase-delay connections were included. Strengths of our approach included the fact that our spatial working memory prediction findings were derived using region pairs (Almeida et al., 2015; Jones & Wilson, 2005; MacKey & Curtis, 2017; Salimi et al., 2021; Siapas et al., 2005; Wager & Smith, 2003; Wirt & Hyman, 2017), the frequency band, and the network topology measure known to be implicated in spatial working memory (Bauer et al., 2021; Dai et al., 2017; Fell & Axmacher, 2011; Hyman et al., 2010; Jones & Wilson, 2005; Siapas

et al., 2005), specified *a priori*. Consistent with our findings, a small, cross-sectional prior study (Jian et al., 2017) found that including versus excluding zero-phase-delay connectivity substantially increased the variance explained in predicting current task state. It showed that predictive ability was not dependent on differing characteristics between functional connectivity methods besides the inclusion or exclusion of zero-phase-delay connectivity: it excluded zero-phase-delay connectivity using a large Laplacian while keeping the connectivity method constant.

Conversely, zero-phase-exclusive methods did demonstrate some advantages. In agreement with others (Hipp et al., 2012; Nolte et al., 2004; Vinck et al., 2011), it appeared that zero-phase-exclusive methods likely minimised artefactual connectivity due to volume conduction and signal leakage: functional connectivity between neighbouring region pairs was minimal when using them (Fig. 4). However, valid functional connections are also most commonly present between nearby region pairs (Bassett & Bullmore, 2017; Honey et al., 2009; Mehrkanoon et al., 2014; Varela et al., 2001), and were not reliably captured by zero-phase-exclusive methods (Figs. 2 and 4).

Quantifying “true” zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity has not been previously achieved in empirical EEG or MEG data. Our approach to identify the distance between region pairs where the effects of signal leakage were likely negligible was novel. Previous approaches have used simulated data (Anzolin et al., 2019; Gohel et al., 2017), with findings consistent with ours. However, simulated data cannot yet accurately inform us about the proportion of “true” cortico-cortical functional connectivity that occurs with zero- and near-zero phase delay, as even the most biologically realistic simulations (Moran et al., 2013) cannot accurately model the emergent properties of whole-cortex connectivity (Engel et al., 1991; Mill et al., 2017; Uhlhaas et al., 2009). Therefore, unlike simulated data approaches, our approach can illustrate that most cortical functional connectivity occurs at zero- or near-zero phase delay, and that excluding it has deleterious effects on the properties of biomarkers derived from functional connectivity metrics. While the extent of artefactual zero-phase-delay connectivity in empirical signals is dependent on methodological choices, our findings highlight that zero- and near-zero-phase-delay synchronisation comprises a substantial proportion of “true” neural interactions.

A key strength of our functional connectivity metric performance assessment approach was the use of convergence across performance criteria—each based on different modalities not trivially correlated with each other. Previous attempts at assessing the validity of zero-

phase-inclusive versus zero-phase-exclusive methods have used single measures of functional connectivity performance (Brookes et al., 2012; Colclough et al., 2016; Hipp et al., 2012), which may lead to bias (Fraschini et al., 2019; Noble et al., 2021). Even using (only) two modalities could be misleading: for example, both structural connectivity and functional connectivity from zero-phase-inclusive methods are more reliable with decreasing Euclidean distance between region pairs (Calamante, 2019; Jbabdi & Johansen-Berg, 2011). Thus, high structure–function concordance may reflect reliable but artefactual functional connectivity correlating with reliable and valid structural connectivity at small distances. Therefore, our use of non-neuroimaging markers of performance was important.

An additional strength was our multi-site study design; our most unexpected finding (negative structure–function concordance with Img COH) was reproduced when analysing each study site separately. Next, as a measure to assess convergence against, the structural connectome has high inter- and intra-individual reliability (Chu et al., 2015; Dennis et al., 2012). Further, to test each functional connectivity metric property, we used multiple analysis approaches, with consistent results.

Is high test–retest reliability a good measure of functional connectivity metric performance? High reliability has been used as evidence of the presence of volume conduction or signal leakage artefact in functional connectivity analyses (Colclough et al., 2016; Nagy et al., 2024). Further, high validity may be present with low test–retest reliability: brain regions functionally connected at one moment may vary from the next. However, in the context of a candidate prognostic or diagnostic biomarker, high test–retest reliability is crucial; it establishes the upper limit of its predictive validity (Carmines & Zeller, 1979).

4.1. Limitations

Our study has important limitations. While we aimed to identify where the effects of signal leakage were negligible, the use of EEG additionally introduced volume conduction artefact (Wolters et al., 2004). In sensor space, artefactual connectivity due to volume conduction has a non-linear relationship with scalp distance (Srinivasan et al., 2007), making it challenging to account for. Source reconstruction aims to limit volume conduction artefact (He et al., 2019): in source space, simulated data show that artefactual connectivity due to volume conduction decreases with increasing Euclidean distance (Anzolin et al., 2019). This makes our approach to determine areas of minimal signal leakage also relevant to volume conduction. Further, EEG is a ubiquitous tool in research and

clinical settings (Mclane et al., 2015), a strength when attempting to identify candidate biomarkers.

Inherent to any source–space analysis, the ill-posed nature of the inverse problem necessitates a sequence of methodological decisions, each of which can influence downstream results. Our findings are based on one such pipeline, using an adaptive LCMV beamformer for the inverse solution and the first principal component to represent time series within each brain region. However, different inverse solutions can lead to adjacency matrices with differing topologies (Mahjoory et al., 2017). While alternative inverse solutions, such as those from the Minimum Norm Estimate (MNE) family (e.g., wMNE, eLORETA), have advantages over LCMV under certain conditions (Halder et al., 2019), the opposite (Nguyen-Danse et al., 2021) or no superiority between methods (Finger et al., 2016; Halder et al., 2019; Hincapié et al., 2017; Mahjoory et al., 2017) have also been found. Relevant to the aims of our study, adaptive LCMV beamformers have shown superiority over the MNE family in the context of biomarker performance (Nguyen-Danse et al., 2021).

A limitation of LCMV beamforming is that highly correlated source activity may bias the location of sources and attenuate their power (Belardinelli et al., 2012; Sekihara et al., 2002, 2004). Zero-phase-delay source interactions, by definition, are highly correlated. Attenuation of such interactions in our data may under-estimate the proportion of “true” zero-phase-delay functional connectivity. This limitation, therefore, strengthens our conclusion about the predominance of “true” zero-phase-delay connectivity. However, this limitation is primarily evidenced by theoretical proofs and simulations (Hincapié et al., 2017; Sekihara et al., 2002, 2004). Empirical quantifications using a phantom-head model (Belardinelli et al., 2012) found that altered source localisation and power attenuation were only substantial between region pairs with near-perfect correlation ($r = .95$) and/or at very small Euclidean distances (1.5 cm). At a Euclidean distance of 3 cm and a signal correlation coefficient of $r = .55$ (consistent with our dataset—see “coherence” in Fig. 4), these biases were minimal. In our dataset, only 5.6% of all region pairs are < 3 cm apart.

The spatial resolution of the source reconstructed signals would have likely improved if we used more scalp electrodes (Lantz et al., 2003; Sohrabpour et al., 2015). We used 64-channel EEG as a compromise between adequate spatial resolution and minimising participant burden (and associated data attrition), given that our participants were aged as young as 6 years.

We only included a limited number of functional connectivity methods, guided by *a priori* defined inclusion criteria. Therefore, we did not investigate several valid

functional connectivity methods (e.g., Baselice et al., 2019; Fraser & Swinney, 1986; King et al., 2013). However, previous work (Jian et al., 2017) shows that the effects of including versus excluding zero-phase-delay interactions are unlikely to be driven by idiosyncratic properties of the pairs of methods compared. Our findings are, therefore, likely to generalise to other bivariate E/MEG functional connectivity methods.

4.2. Future directions

Future methodological approaches should aim to account for artefactual functional connectivity by approaches other than suppressing all zero-phase-delay connectivity. An example of an advance in this direction is the Phase Shift Invariant Imaging of Coherent Sources (PSIICOS) method (Ossadtchi et al., 2018), which aims to suppress signal leakage while retaining “true” zero-phase-delay functional connectivity. Unlike conventional pipelines which first reconstruct source activity and then quantify their interactions, it aims to reconstruct source *interactions* by applying a projection to the sensor-space cross-spectral density matrix. Although PSIICOS requires a trade-off between the extent of signal leakage versus “true” signal suppressed—and may produce false positive interactions under certain conditions—it provides a framework that has been iteratively improved (Altukhov et al., 2023; Kleeva & Ossadtchi, 2025) and appears promising.

To validate and extend our findings across modalities, these analyses should be replicated using MEG. MEG has the advantage of requiring only signal leakage and not volume conduction to be accounted for, making our approach (Fig. 1a) to determine the distance where artefactual zero-phase-delay connectivity is minimal readily applicable.

4.3. Perspective

To some extent, our findings are surprising given the field’s move towards favouring zero-phase-exclusive methods (Garcés et al., 2022; Hipp et al., 2012; Miljevic et al., 2022; Nolte et al., 2004). Zero-phase-exclusive methods were introduced to identify “true” brain interactions as opposed to trivial artefact (Nolte et al., 2004; Vinck et al., 2011). Over the last 20+ years, they have consistently been published as improvements on their corresponding zero-phase-inclusive methods. This position has been adopted by several studies attempting to identify candidate diagnostic or prognostic biomarkers (Garcés et al., 2022; Miljevic et al., 2022; Sato et al., 2023).

The presence of “true” zero-phase-delay synchrony in brain is unintuitive: action potential transmission delays

due to axonal conduction and synaptic transmission are in the order of tens of milliseconds (Uhlhaas et al., 2009; Vicente et al., 2008). Such time delays would cause substantial phase delays between connected brain regions. Thus, zero-phase-delay functional connectivity across distant neural populations would not be possible if the brain was a simple linear system. A leading postulated mechanism for zero-phase-delay connectivity is “resonance-induced synchrony” (Gollo et al., 2014): bidirectional information transfer between regions acts to mutually alter their dynamics into a stable zero-phase-delay pattern. Key structures have empirically shown to facilitate this, including cortico-thalamo-cortical loops (Uhlhaas et al., 2009; Vicente et al., 2008) and the corpus callosum (Bloom & Hynd, 2005; Musgrave & Gloor, 1980; Vicente et al., 2008; however, see Contreras et al., 1996). Other hypothesised mechanisms of zero-phase-delay synchrony include entrainment (Gray & McCormick, 1996) and emergence (Kopell et al., 2000). It is possible that multiple mechanisms work in unison (Vicente et al., 2008).

The debate central to our study is the extent to which measured zero- and near-zero phase-delay connectivity in source reconstructed data is artefactual versus “true.” We found that most functional connectivity occurred with zero- and near-zero phase delays, even when signal leakage was likely negligible. Converging lines of evidence demonstrate that including zero-phase-delay functional connectivity increases the performance of functional connectivity metrics as biomarkers. These findings challenge generally accepted assumptions that zero-phase-exclusive methods are superior to zero-phase-inclusive methods.

DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

The LEAP Study data are available here, subject to an approved data application: <https://redcap.pasteur.fr/surveys/?s=YRFF78PH89>. Code is available here: <https://github.com/cmehra-brain>.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Chirag Mehra: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing—Original draft, Writing—Review and editing, and Visualisation. Ahmad Beyh: Formal analysis, Writing—Original draft, Writing—Review and editing, Visualisation. Petroula Laiou: Resources and Writing—Original draft. Pilar Garces: Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing—Review and editing. Emily J.H. Jones: Writing—Review and editing, Funding acquisition, and Project administration. Luke Mason: Data curation and Project administration. Jan Buitelaar: Writing—Review and editing, Funding acquisition, and Project administration.

Mark H. Johnson: Project administration. Declan Murphy: Funding acquisition and Project administration. Eva Loth: Writing—Review and editing, Funding acquisition, and Project administration. Flavio Dell’Acqua: Formal analysis, Writing—Review and editing, Funding acquisition, Project administration, and Supervision. Joshua B. Ewen: Conceptualisation, Writing—Review and editing, and Supervision. Mark P. Richardson: Writing—Review and editing, Supervision, and Funding acquisition. Jonathan O’Muircheartaigh: Writing—Review and editing, Supervision, and Funding acquisition.

FUNDING

This work was supported by EU-AIMS (European Autism Interventions), which received support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 115300, the resources of which are composed of financial contributions from the European Union’s Seventh Framework Programme (grant FP7/2007-2013), from the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations companies’ in-kind contributions, and from Autism Speaks. The results leading to this publication have also received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 777394 for the project AIMS-2-TRIALS. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA and AUTISM SPEAKS, Autistica, and SFARI. This study was also delivered through the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Maudsley Biomedical Research Centre (BRC). J.O.M. was funded by a Sir Henry Dale Fellowship jointly by the Wellcome Trust and the Royal Society (206675/Z/17/Z). J.O.M. received support from the Medical Research Council Centre for Neurodevelopmental Disorders, King’s College London [MR/N026063/1]. None of the funders had a role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results. Any views expressed are those of the author(s) and not necessarily those of any of the funders, the NIHR, or the Department of Health and Social Care.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

Joshua B. Ewen previously consulted for Novartis. In the past 3 years, Jan Buitelaar has been a consultant to/member of advisory board of/and/or speaker for Takeda, Medice, Angelini, Neuraxpharm and Bitsphi. He is not an employee of any of these companies, and not a stock shareholder of any of these companies. He has no other financial or material support, including expert testimony,

patents, royalties. Pilar Garces is employed by Roche Innovation Center, Basel, Switzerland. No other author has competing interests to declare.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to the AIMS-2-TRIALS LEAP-group for data collection and quality control procedures. We are grateful to Dr. Piotr J. Franaszczuk for his expert advice on signal analysis and filtering and to Prof. Dr Christine Ecker and team for pre-processing the T1-weighted MR images. We are grateful to the reviewers for their help in improving our study.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Supplementary material for this article is available with the online version here: <https://doi.org/10.1162/IMAG.a.985>.

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